

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VASILIU-FELTES****FIRST NAME: INGRID****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (owned account prior to EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., M

Key Concepts

1. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-36)
2. Language Nuances (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-30, 58)
3. Equality (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 29)
4. Stereotyping (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 30)
5. Political Nuances (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 29)

COMPLEXITIES AND NUANCES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Generating novel ideas and viewpoints with unambiguousness and exactness is crucial in the academic domain. Academic writing is often regarded as a complex endeavor, as it involves a multitude of writing skills that serve a variety of industries, disciplines, and interdisciplinary purposes. The requirement is for rigorous formatting, just as much as for original content. There are some rules that overlap and others that are unique to a specific writing style. Many styles, including the Turabian style, have been developed to suit different industry or topic-specific needs. There are several crucial differences between various accepted writing styles and some common features, such as those covering plagiarism, originality, quotations, citations, grammar, syntax, and writing clarity.

a) Importance of Originality

While **originality** is related to plagiarism, they are not the same. Plagiarism happens when someone fails to give correct credit for work that is not their own. There is a straightforward way to teach students how to avoid this. It is much more difficult to offer guidance on the creative process of generating new content, including concepts,

frameworks, perspectives, or opinions. Additionally, we must be careful not to confuse the intentional act of not crediting authors when quoting their work with not having enough knowledge to do so. The ACA-401 coursepack offers extremely helpful advice on these subjects. For instance, it instructs students on the correct ways of introducing quotations, including using a "signal phrase." These signal phrases can alert the reader that a quotation is about to happen and ensure a nice blending of the quotation with the student's original content (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 37).

Paraphrasing is one of the rules of academic writing students find especially hard to master. Paraphrasing well—to produce something that is genuine and original yet accurate and faithful to the meaning of the source—requires a lot of reading, understanding, and reflection, which most students find challenging.

The recent large-scale adoption of artificial intelligence tools has further amplified the risk of plagiarism and can potentially negatively impact students' ability to generate original content. As highlighted in a recent publication by Nguyen et al., human and AI collaboration is evolving and is clearly influencing academic writing (Nguyen et al. 2024, 1-18).

b) Language Nuances

Academic writing projects require attention to and consideration of many different **language** variations, such as British versus American English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25). Being cognizant of historic Yiddish, Black, and Latin influences also fosters clarity and avoids confusion in the academic content we aim to convey (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 30). The correct approach is to use the kind of language that anticipated audiences can understand and are comfortable with.

c) Equality

In addition to all foundational elements of academic writing -grammar and syntax, correct punctuation, accurate quotations, and the nuanced use of language—it is also essential to follow **equality** guidelines in academic writing. To be inclusive and diverse involves much more diligence than only following a particular style or method; it is about being committed to fairness and respect for everyone. This is a topic that is worth reading and engaging with more deeply because it requires continuous learning from a diverse global academic community. One way to exemplify this in practice is to avoid the term "chairman," which is not inclusive. Instead, one can use "chairperson" or "chair," terms that are more likely to be free of gender stereotyping.

d) Stereotyping

Not **stereotyping** in our academic writing requires more than just language pattern awareness; it relies on an understanding of multiple complex factors. The ACA-401 Coursepack identifies a number of specific stereotypes that writers must avoid. These

include gender (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 29), cultural, ethnic, and socioeconomic stereotypes, as well as stereotypes based on education and geographic region (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 30). Inclusive and diverse academic writing is both a basic courtesy and a requirement of the writing and ethical codes of the academic community. It also allows our work to be understood by a wide range of readers and engenders trust within the community.

e) Political Nuances

One of the most difficult areas for students to master in academic writing is the careful use of **political** terminology—terms for which their meanings may have shifted, sometimes dramatically, over the last few decades. It is not enough to have a passing acquaintanceship with recent history; successful and thoughtful academic writers must be tuned in to the current political climate. We must have a good reason for using the terms we do, especially when there are alternatives available, and we must be especially vigilant to not disrespect any of our readers. Examples include using "chair" or "chairperson" instead of "chairman" or "stay at home mom" instead of house-wife, or "Native American" replacing "Indian" to more accurately and respectfully refer to Indigenous peoples (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 29).

2) CONCLUSION

Concise and clear, the *ACA-401 Coursepack* provides direction on writing socially responsible, academic prose. The first chapter describes the basic components of an academic essay, while the next chapters elaborate on several crucial components of an academic essay, such as plagiarism, vocabulary, abbreviations, and expressions.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Nguyen, Andy, Yvonne Hong, Belle Dang, and Xiaoshan Huang. 2024. "Human-AI Collaboration Patterns in AI-Assisted Academic Writing." *Studies in Higher Education* 1-18.

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